

GOAL: Future Commons is a proposal to establish an international Research and Mobilisation Partnership (RMP) to investigate, understand, and where appropriate facilitate the adoption of Open Research Practices (ORP) as a default by researchers, research users, and research brokers.

PARTNERSHIP APPROACH AND PROGRAM: Future Commons is a cross-sector and interdisciplinary network that co-creates, leverages, and channels new and existing research, networking, and knowledge mobilization activities of its partners and participants, many of whom are leading institutions or individuals in this domain. As such it touches on the objectives of the Insight, Connection, and Talent programmes, with an emphasis on Insight and Connection:

RELEVANCE AND SIGNIFICANCE TO PARTNERS: The partnership consists of three types of institutions:

- **Type I (Universities, Research Institutes, Libraries, and Museums):** Organisations such as universities, university libraries, research institutes, and similar organisations that engage with but have not been created specifically to promote ORP and are the locus where most publicly-funded research occurs;
- **Type II (Open Research Advocacy and Mobilisation Organisations):** Organisations, such as current partners **SPARC** and **FORCE11**, that are more directly involved in the development and mobilisation of ORP;
- **Type III (Scholarly Societies, Funders, and (Quasi-)Government Entities):** Organisations that are vitally engaged with questions involving ORP but are not primarily devoted to their promotion or dissemination: e.g. scholarly societies; quasi governmental organisations; and (where permissible) private and public funding agencies. These organisations strive to represent the opinion of investigators within their disciplines and can be a vector for mobilisation. Their role is a significant research question in its own right.

HOW DOES FUTURE COMMONS COMPLEMENT OTHER OPEN SCIENCE INITIATIVES? Future Commons complements the efforts of other agencies, institutions and consortia by focussing on the cultural change among individual researchers that will be required if Open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) Research Practices are to become the global default.

Most current and previous initiatives in this area have focussed on external, structural and economic issues in Open Research: the economic models, infrastructure and tools, government and institutional policies, and incentive and rewards systems that must change if traditional “closed” research and dissemination practices are to be disrupted.

Future Commons complements this work by focussing on questions of cultural change and individual motivation: What impediments prevent the widespread adoption of Open Practices by the global

Research Community? What differences are there in the adoption of Open Research Practices in different disciplines, regions, and generations? How can we understand and facilitate investigator buy-in to Open and FAIR Research Practices? Are there times when Open Research Practices are inappropriate, unethical, or otherwise suboptimal?

Future Commons provides our partners with a space for developing and coordinating their efforts in Open Research. We intend to supplement and support outreach and mobilisation efforts by our Partner institutions and provide support for research, mobilisation, and cross-silo networking efforts focussed on promoting Open Research Practice to individual researchers.

CONTEXT: The context for our proposal is the degree to which research practices have not been disrupted by the development of the Web and subsequent technologies. \

There are many reasons why these changes have not caused the system-wide disruption seen in other industries. These issues are compounded by academia's traditionally fragmented organisation. The result is a surprisingly low level of popular engagement and support for ORP within the research community.

ORIGINALITY AND SIGNIFICANCE: The lack of support for ORP among researchers often has been commented upon. Researchers, publishers, librarians, and others are exhorted to “provid[e] education where there are misconceptions” even as it is acknowledged that this outreach is “tiring and takes a lot of effort”. But how this outreach should or could be done has been less clear. While individuals and institutions working in this space often devote considerable attention to the mobilization of information about ORP, their work tends to take place within the disciplinary, regional, and/or sectoral silo(s) in which they operate, and focus on specific activities, tools, policies, standards, or models. National funding agencies tend to focus their educational and mobilization efforts on the citizens who are eligible for their support. Groups that are interested in Open Data focus their outreach on data-centric questions. Publishers and scholarly societies educate those who work in their domains and disciplines. Organisations in the Global North and Global South tend to focus on those living in their respective regions. Very little work is done on a cross-silo basis or focussed on the motivations of the individual researchers and communities that lie at the heart of the endeavour.

EXPECTED CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE: Future Commons is about addressing this problem of investigator buy-in directly. Our goal is to provide an intellectual and organisational infrastructure to gather, incubate, and mobilise best practice in the use and adoption of ORP by individual researchers across disciplinary, regional, linguistic, and sectoral boundaries; to explore why many researchers have been reluctant to adopt ORP; investigate why adoption is higher or lower in some sectors, regions, and disciplines; and to share and promote best practice in the development and mobilisation of ORP across these boundaries. To the degree that resistance from the research community has proved to be among the most significant obstacles to the adoption of several high profile ORP policies and initiatives, our focus on the “last mile” of investigator buy-in complements and leverages efforts of others in this domain: the widespread adoption of ORP requires good policies, infrastructure, models, and incentives; but as

numerous efforts to roll out OA policies on a national or regional level in its absence have demonstrated. As far as we are aware, this is the first international project devoted specifically to investigator uptake.

APPROACH AND METHOD: We base our work on two key premises about the present state of Scholarly Communication:

- P1.** That transformative change towards Open Research Practices will require sustained and broad popular and practical support from the research world's scholars, scientists, editors, and publishers, similar to that largely already achieved among its funders, governments, universities, libraries, and policy makers.
- P2.** That developing such popular consensus will require us to learn across and transcend disciplinary, national, regional, sectoral, and other types of fragmentation that traditionally characterise work in this area.

These in turn lead to four main research questions:

- Q1.** *Why and to what degree has the adoption of ORP by the research community lagged similarly disruptive changes in other industries? (P1)*
- Q2.** *What differences exist in the adoption of ORP within different sectors, regions, and disciplines? (P2)*
- Q3.** *What strategies are proven best to mobilise the adoption of ORP within the research community? (P1 and P2)*
- Q4.** *Under what conditions is the adoption of ORP not appropriate or ethical? How can these be reconciled with the goal of allowing as wide access and usage as possible to research? (P1 and P2)*

We will approach these questions using three main methods:

- M1.** *Identify, generate, and disseminate knowledge needed to understand and, where appropriate, successfully mobilise ORP among investigators across sectors, disciplines, and regions;*
- M2.** *Incubate community development, exchange, and implementation of best practices in ORP and their mobilisation on a cross-silo basis, focussing particularly on Highly Qualified Personnel (HQP), early career researchers (ECR), and researchers from Middle and Low Income Economies (MLIC);*
- M3.** *Mobilize the results of M1 and M2 through the improved use of existing approaches and the development of new programmes.*

INVOLVEMENT OF/BENEFITS TO THE PARTNER ORGANISATIONS: Partner Organisations will have a majority vote (minimum 50%+1) on the Advisory Board and through their representatives on this board responsibility for approving non-affiliated community volunteers to the Board and the composition of the Steering Committee.

Other than participation in the governance of the project, the main benefit to the Partners comes from their ability to assist in establishing the Partnership's goals and participating in its activities including proposing research and mobilisation projects or receiving funds to support graduate students and other HQP.

TRAINING AND MENTORING PLANS: Training and Mentoring is a core activity of this partnership. The overall goal of the Partnership is to investigate, understand, and facilitate the transfer of knowledge of ORP to the current and next generation of researchers and students across regions, disciplines, and sectors. A major component of our Incubation activity (**M2**) involves supporting student exchanges, internships, and study-fellowships focussing on developing knowledge of and capacity in ORP. Our seed fund competitions too will follow the successful model from our PDG and particularly support applications from students, ECRs, and MLIC researchers. Since students and ECRs have played a notable role in the formation of many startup companies in the ORP space, we also anticipate an outsized benefit for this community from our proposed Startup Micro Grants.

The other two activities, however, also have a large training component. Mobilisation activities (M3) such as FSCI and especially OpenCon (which is a by-invitation gathering specifically of students and ECRs) are student friendly and will devote considerable funds to supporting student participation through travel and tuition bursaries. Perhaps most importantly, however, the majority of our student and postdoctoral fellowships will go towards supporting students engaged in research on ORP within the Observatory (**M1**) at our partner institutions (primarily Type I). Participation by these partners is headed by many of the leading researchers in this space, providing an unparalleled opportunity for students and ECRs to train with ORP thought-leaders. Approximately 40% of our proposal is currently budgeted for these positions.

KNOWLEDGE MOBILISATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES: Knowledge Mobilisation and Dissemination Activities are core to **M1** (Identify, Generate, and Disseminate knowledge) and M3 (Mobilise the results of **M1** and **M2**). The Observatory (**M1**) will develop, disseminate, and house research and data on the problem of investigator uptake of ORP along several planes (see above). Mobilisation activities such as FSCI and OpenCon (M3) have already established a track record in ensuring that the latest developments in ORP are pushed out to researchers and others in a usable form.

POTENTIAL IMPACT AND INFLUENCE: In as much as the investigator is at the heart of the research enterprise and weak investigator uptake has proved a major stumbling block for several international ORP initiatives, the potential impact of this proposal is very large: our partners are leading national and international actors in the research, development, and promotion of ORP; this proposal leverages and extends their already significant work to address a persistent stumbling block in the development of national and international policy.

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About the Funding Programme

Future Commons is in the process of developing an application to the Canadian Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) Partnership Programme for 6 year/\$2.5 million (CAD) in funding. This funding will support both the development of a virtual observatory and three main streams of activity: Networking and Facilitation, Incubation, and Mobilisation (A previous \$200,000 grant from SSHRC's Partnership Development Grant Programme helped support the initial formation of the Partnership and funded the development of activities such as the Force11 Scholarly Communication Institute).

BASIC INFORMATION ON THE SSHRC PARTNERSHIP PROGRAMME¹: The SSHRC Partnership Grant competition is unusual in several respects:

1. It is awarded to institutions rather than individuals. The grant is prepared by a director on behalf of a lead institution (in this case the University of Lethbridge).
2. It requires participation by other institutional partners (Canadian or International)
3. Unlike other SSHRC grants, non-resident individuals may be listed as “Co-applicants” (normally they may only be collaborators); the grant can pay direct research costs for non-Canadian resident co-applicants and institutions.
4. The competition requires applicants to secure the equivalent of an additional 35% of the amount requested from SSHRC in cash or in-kind “contributions” from its partners.

CONTRIBUTIONS: “Contributions” consist cash or in-kind donations to the activity of the programme; this greatly reduces the opportunity cost of participating, since many partners “donate” resources they are already planning to spend on the activities that make the grant attractive to them in the first place. As a result, many applications to the Partnership Programme are leveraged at more than 1:1.

Even with this definition, however, partners are not required to make a contribution as a condition for joining the grant. While the best partners for this grant are institutions that are already active or planning to become active in Open Research since those activities can be counted as a contribution, Future Commons is prepared to consider applications from organisations that are not spending in this area.

COMPETITION PROCESS AND TIMELINES: The competition is run in two stages:

Stage 1. Prospective Partnerships submit a reduced application indicating their proposed programme of activity and current and proposed partners (Due Feb 15, 2019). At this stage only broad budget costs are required and partnerships may still be prospective. Successful applicants at this stage are awarded \$20k (CAD) to prepare a full application for Stage 2.

Stage 2. Applicants who were successful at Stage 1 are invited to submit a full application detailing their programme of activity, partners, and a detailed budget (November 30, 2019).

Recently, the final success rate for the competition as a whole has been about 20-25% of total applications to Stage 1. SSHRC has indicated that more money is available in 2019-2020.

¹ Please note: This is an unofficial summary. For official details please see the SSHRC website.